

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Low percolation threshold of polypropylene specially designed graphene nanocomposites

Karolina Gaska¹, Roland Kádár¹, Thomas Gkourmpis²

¹ Department of Industrial and Materials Science, Engineering Materials, Chalmers University of Technology, Gothenburg, Sweden

² Innovation & Technology, Borealis AB, Stenungsund, Sweden

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Available graphene

Few-layers graphene (FLG) or multilayer graphene (MLG, G)

Graphene oxide (GO), incl. FLG, MLG, GnP

Chemically modified graphene prepared by oxidation (high oxygen content).

Graphite nanoplatelets (GnP)

> 10 LG

< 100 nm

(over 100 nm -> milled graphite powders)

Reduced graphene oxide (rGO)

Processed by chemical, thermal, microwave, photo-chemical, photo-thermal or microbial/bacterial methods to reduce its oxygen content.

Graphene composites - different processing methods

The vast majority of 'bulk graphene'

>> 10 monolayers
Graphite nanoplatelets (GnP)

Röding, M., Gaska, K., Kádár, R., Lorén, N. (2017) ACS Applied Nano Materials 1(1), 160-167

Gaska, K., Kádár, R., Rybak, A., Siwek, A., Gubanski, S. (2017) Polymers (Switzerland) 9(7), 11

Gaska K, Xu X., Gubanski S., Kádár R. (2017) Polymers (Switzerland) 9(11), 294

Low shear rates - alignment achieved

Main focus: Flow-field-matrix-filler(s) interactions

Graphene, even when available

(<10 monolayers)

- ✗ Agglomerates easily
- ✗ High percolation thresholds
- ✗ Low compatibility with polymers

Composites preparation

Goal: industrially-relevant, simple process

No pre-treatment!
Matrix: Polypropylene (PP), linear topology,
high molecular weight

Batch melt mixing
Brabender Type: W50
10min, 50RPM

**Compression
moulding**

**Electrical,
Rheological,
Thermal,
Mechanical**

Instrumentation:

- Hot Disk thermal analyser
- DSC
- TGA
- Electrical conductivity measurement setup

Available graphene

SDG - specially designed graphene

Few-layers graphene (FLG) or multilayer graphene (MLG, G)

Graphite nanoplatelets (GnP)

> 10 LG

< 100 nm

(over 100 nm -> milled graphite powders)

Graphene oxide (GO), incl. FLG, MLG, GnP

Chemically modified graphene prepared by oxidation (high oxygen content).

Reduced graphene oxide (rGO)

Processed by chemical, thermal, microwave, photo-chemical, photo-thermal or microbial/bacterial methods to reduce its oxygen content.

Electrical conductivity

Very low percolation threshold!

$$\sigma = \sigma_0(\phi - \phi_c)^t$$

Polymer	Filler Type	Production Method	Percolation Threshold [wt.%]	Reference
PP	SDG	Melt Mixing	~1	Our work
	Graphene Platelets	Melt Mixing	9	Li J. Et al. 2007
	Expanded Graphite	Melt Mixing	8-12	Pionteck J. 2015
	Graphene Platelets	Melt Mixing	8-6	Zhang J. 2017
	Graphene Platelets	Melt Mixing	8	Strååt, M. 2011
	Graphene Platelets	Melt Mixing	12	Kalaitzidou K. 2007
	Graphene Platelets	Melt Mixing	8-12	Li Y. 2011

Below percolation

2.5 wt.%

5.0 wt.%

topography map current map

<http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/2053-1583/aac055/pdf>

Conclusions

- In this work, we have presented an industrially relevant melt-mixed system of polypropylene and specially designed graphene.
- Due to its unique structure, the filler has the potential to create a three-dimensional extended structure, thus allowing for a very efficient dispersion.
- The dispersion efficiency can be seen via the excessively **low electrical percolation threshold** observed by this study.
- The influence of graphene on thermal properties has been also investigated.

CHALMERS
UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

ICCM22
MELBOURNE
AUSTRALIA

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

#ICCM22